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A novel photochromic film based on preyssler heteropolyacid and gold nanoparticles as a green and recyclable nanocatalyst for removal of azo dye from wastewaters

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Abstract

Using photolysis method, Preyssler acid, H₁₄[NaP₅W₃₀O₁₁₀], was employed in the form of composite film as a green reductant and stabilizer for the synthesis of Au nanoparticles. The synthesized Au NPs/Preyssler film was prepared by a simple and fast sol-gel method and characterized by UV-Visible spectroscopy, particle size distribution, Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FESEM), and Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS) analysis. Our findings showed that Au nanoparticles were obtained at about 6-11 nm and were readily inserted and monodispersed in the nanocomposite film. The photocatalytic performance of this NPs/Preyssler film was examined in decolorization of methyl orange (MeO) in aqueous media. UV-Visible studies showed that Au NPs/Preyssler film can efficiently catalyze the decolorization of the aforementioned azo dye. The pseudo-first-order rate constants were also calculated for this reaction.

Keyword

Decolorization, Gold nanoparticles, Heteropolyacid, Nanocatalyst, Photochromic film, Preyssler, Azo dyes, Composite films, Fiber optic sensors, Gold, Gold alloys, Metal nanoparticles, Nanoparticles, Particle size, Particle, size analysis, Photolysis, Rate constants, Sol-gel process, Sol-gels, Synthesis (chemical), Heteropoly acids, Nano catalyst, azo dye, gold nanoparticle, hydroxyl group, methyl orange, nanocomposite, Article, controlled study, dispersion.